

Overcoming Frequency Resolution Limits Using a Solid-State Spin Quantum Sensor

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The ability to determine precisely the separation of two frequencies is fundamental to spectroscopy, yet the resolution limit poses a critical challenge: distinguishing two incoherent signals becomes impossible when their frequencies are sufficiently close. Here, we demonstrate a simple and powerful approach, dubbed *superresolution quantum sensing*, which experimentally resolves two nearly identical incoherent signals using a solid-state spin quantum sensor. By carefully choosing interrogation times that satisfy the superresolution condition, we eliminate quantum projection noise, overcoming the vanishing distinguishability of signals with near-identical frequencies. This leads to improved resolution, which scales as t^{-2} in comparison to the standard t^{-1} scaling. Together with a greatly reduced classical readout noise assisted by a nuclear spin, we are able to achieve sub-kHz resolution with a signal detection time of 80 μ s. Our results highlight the potential of quantum sensing to overcome conventional frequency resolution limitations, with broad implications for precision measurements.

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Quantum metrology and quantum sensing employ the fundamental laws of quantum physics to achieve precision that is typically not feasible with classical analogs [1,2]. For example, reaching the fundamental quantum Cramér-Rao bound has allowed for resolution of two weak thermal optical point sources with a distance below the diffraction limit [3–6]. The ability to nullify measurement projection noise by coherent control and a suitable measurement basis provides a critical resource for solving the frequency resolution problem: when the separation between frequencies vanishes, the uncertainty to distinguish them becomes divergent. Minimizing quantum projection noise mitigates this effect and leads to a finite uncertainty, allowing to

overcome resolution limits with quantum sensing of noisy signals [7,8].

Frequency resolution problems are crucial in science and technology. As a prominent example, in nanoscale nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), dominated by statistical nuclear polarization, the spin precession in an external magnetic field typically generates oscillating magnetic signals with short coherence times [9–11]. This poses severe challenges in determining complex spectra with quantum sensors [8,12], even with advanced quantum sensing techniques, such as correlation spectroscopy [13–20] and quantum heterodyne detection [21–24].

Here, we use a solid-state quantum sensor of a single NV center in diamond to overcome the frequency resolution limit. By meticulously choosing the interrogation time to satisfy a superresolution condition [7], we simultaneously nullify the quantum projection noise and maximize its response to frequency separation. We also improve the readout technique of the solid-state spin sensor by using an ancilla nuclear memory spin [16–18,25–27], reducing classical readout noise and improving resolution. We achieve discrimination of two incoherent time-oscillating signals with a frequency separation below the Fourier limit down to the sub-kHz regime, using a solid-state spin with a single measurement detection time of only 80 μ s. We demonstrate the method in the context of pulsed dynamical

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decoupling and Ramsey sequences, allowing for detection of frequencies from dc to several tens of MHz [1]. Our approach resolves a fundamental limitation in spectroscopy, paving the way for high-resolution nanoscale NMR.

Principles of superresolution quantum sensing—Spectral resolution problems typically involve a time oscillating signal, interacting with a probe, see Fig. 1(a). By extracting information, encoded in the probe, one can estimate the signal frequencies, e.g., ω_1 and ω_2 . Resolution becomes challenging when $\omega_1 \rightarrow \omega_2$, as the uncertainty of the frequency separation estimate $\Delta(\omega_1 - \omega_2) \rightarrow \infty$. As an explicit example, we consider nano NMR sensing where the effect of the signal on the qubit sensor is characterized by the Hamiltonian [10]

$$H_s = \sum_{i=1,2} \Omega_i \sin[\omega_i t + \varphi_i(t)] \sigma_z, \quad (1)$$

where Ω_i are the signal amplitudes at the two frequencies, and $\varphi_i(t)$ are their phases, which can vary in time. It is useful to define the angular frequency difference $\delta_r = (\omega_1 - \omega_2)/2$ and mean angular frequency $\omega_s = (\omega_1 + \omega_2)/2$. We emphasize that we consider the general scenario of incoherent time-oscillating signals where the phases $\varphi_i(t)$ are uncorrelated between different measurements.

We consider standard Ramsey interferometry where we initialize the sensor qubit in a ground state $|0\rangle$, prepare a coherent superposition state with a $\pi/2$ pulse, and let it evolve for time t under the Hamiltonian in Eq. (1). We focus on the particular case when $\Omega_{1,2} = \Omega$ to correspond with our experimental implementation but the method also works when this condition is not satisfied [7]. The transition probability in the initialization basis is [7]

$$P_t = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \prod_{i=1}^2 J_0 \left(\frac{4\Omega}{\omega_i} \sin \left(\frac{\omega_i t}{2} \right) \right) \right], \quad (2)$$

where $J_0(\cdot)$ is the zeroth order Bessel function. As $\delta_r \rightarrow 0$ we find that $\partial P_t / \partial \delta_r = 0$ [28], leading to the aforementioned resolution problem. The vanishing susceptibility arises from the symmetry of interchanging ω_1 and ω_2 in the case of two closely spaced signals, as shown in Eq. (1).

For small values of δ_r , we can expand the transition probability to its second order, i.e., $P_t \approx a_t + b_t \delta_r^2$ with a_t and b_t functions of $\{\Omega, \omega_s, t\}$ [28]. The resolution lower bound is $\Delta \delta_r \geq 1/\sqrt{\mathcal{I}(\delta_r)}$, where $\mathcal{I}(\delta_r) = (\partial_{\delta_r} P_t)^2 / \sigma_{\text{noise}}^2$ is the Fisher information (FI) [7]. The variance of P_t due to noise is $\sigma_{\text{noise}}^2 = \sigma_{\text{QPN}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{readout}}^2$ with the main contributions typically coming from quantum projection noise (QPN) and photon shot noise affecting the readout, respectively [1]. Then,

$$(\Delta \delta_r)^2 = \frac{\sigma_{\text{QPN}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{readout}}^2}{(\partial_{\delta_r} P_t)^2} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{QPN}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{readout}}^2}{4b_t^2 \delta_r^2}. \quad (3)$$

FIG. 1. Principles of superresolution quantum sensing. (a) Single NV spin as a quantum sensor (with ^{15}N nuclear spin serving as a memory qubit) for detecting two incoherent oscillating signals with the frequencies $\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$ [cf. Eq. (1)]. (b) The transition probability, P_t , displays maximal difference for $\delta_r \equiv (\omega_1 - \omega_2)/2 = 0$ (red curve) and $\delta_r = 0.05\omega_s$ (blue curve), where $\omega_s = (\omega_1 + \omega_2)/2$, in the neighboring region of $\omega_s t = 2n\pi$ with n positive integers, as indicated by the superresolution condition.

The effect of readout noise can be reduced significantly, e.g., by using single-shot-readout [38], making QPN dominant [28]. We carefully choose the interrogation times $t = 2n\pi/\omega_s$ (with n a positive integer) to satisfy the superresolution condition [7]. Then, $P_t \approx \Omega^2 t^2 \delta_r^2 / \omega_s^2$ which results in $\sigma_{\text{QPN}}^2 = P_t(1 - P_t) \approx P_t$ with the approximation valid for small $\delta_r \rightarrow 0$ and $t = 2n\pi/\omega_s$. Although both P_t and σ_{QPN}^2 approach zero as $\delta_r \rightarrow 0$, the FI does not vanish, taking the form

$$\mathcal{I}(\delta_r) = \frac{(\partial_{\delta_r} P_t)^2}{P_t(1 - P_t)} \approx \frac{4\Omega^2 t^2}{\omega_s^2}, \quad (4)$$

so $\Delta \delta_r \geq \omega_s / (2\Omega t)$, which is finite for arbitrarily small δ_r . This is also confirmed in Fig. 1(b), which demonstrates that the local maximal difference between $P_t(\delta_r = 0)$ and $P_t(\delta_r = 0.05\omega_s)$ indeed occurs when the superresolution condition holds, namely $t = 2n\pi/\omega_s$. We note that the method is also applicable with conventional and other readout schemes [39–42] as long as the readout noise is suppressed sufficiently, e.g., by repeating the experiment.

Despite its nonvanishing property, $\mathcal{I}(\delta_r)$ in Eq. (4) is not optimal, as the signal angular frequency ω_s can be quite large. It proves useful to apply a dynamical decoupling sequence of fast, ideally instantaneous, π pulses with a pulse separation $\tau = \pi/\omega_{\text{DD}}$ in the sensing protocol [1,7]. Dynamical decoupling improves the coherence time by applying an effective spectral noise filter with a characteristic sensing frequency $f_{\text{DD}} = 1/(2\tau)$ [1]. The time evolution of the system in the interaction basis of the pulses is given by the Hamiltonian

$$H_{\text{eff}} \approx \sum_{i=1,2} \tilde{\Omega}_i \sin[\delta_i t + \varphi_i(t)] \sigma_z, \quad (5)$$

where $\delta_i = \omega_{\text{DD}} - \omega_i$ ($i = 1, 2$) with $\omega_{\text{DD}} = (2\pi)f_{\text{DD}}$, and $\tilde{\Omega} = (2/\pi)\Omega$ is attenuated due to the pulses (see Fig. 2(a) and [28]). Thus, $\delta_s = \omega_{\text{DD}} - \omega_s$ and $\delta_r = (\delta_2 - \delta_1)/2$ [7], as shown in Fig. 2(a). The pulse separation is nearly

FIG. 2. Experimental protocol using a solid-state spin quantum sensor in diamond. (a) Resolving two angular frequencies, ω_1 and ω_2 , is challenging as they approach each other. We shift $\omega_i \rightarrow \delta_i$ in the interaction basis by applying dynamical decoupling [1] with short π pulses, separated by time π/ω_{DD} . (b) Energy levels of the NV center electron spin with hyperfine coupling to its intrinsic ^{15}N nuclear spin. The $m_s = \pm 1$ energy level degeneracy is lifted by a Zeeman splitting $2\gamma_{\text{NV}}B_z$ with an external magnetic field B_z , aligned with the NV center symmetry axis. The hyperfine coupling further splits each electronic state into two sublevels, $m_I = \pm 1/2$. The nuclear Zeeman splitting, $\gamma_n B_z$, is also taken into account due to the high magnetic field. (c) Sensing and readout sequence. The spin state of the sensor is mapped onto the nuclear spin with a controlled RF π pulse, which can be repetitively read out by single shot readout (SSR) measurements. (d) The histogram of the fluorescence time trace obtained from SSR readout, which can be well fitted by two Gaussian distributions. The high and low counts correspond to a nuclear spin state $|\uparrow\rangle$, and $|\downarrow\rangle$, respectively, giving rise to a high readout fidelity of 99.69%.

resonant with the time-oscillating signal, i.e., $\delta_i \ll \omega_i$, resulting in $\mathcal{I}(\delta_r) \approx 4\tilde{\Omega}^2 t^2 / \delta_s^2$ and $\Delta\delta_r \geq \delta_s / (2\tilde{\Omega}t)$, leading to improved resolution. As the superresolution condition requires $\delta_s = 2n\pi/t$, this leads to $\Delta\delta_r \geq (n\pi/\tilde{\Omega})t^{-2}$, which is much better than the standard t^{-1} scaling.

Experimental implementation—We perform a proof-of-principle experimental implementation of the superresolution protocol using a single nitrogen-vacancy center (NV) in diamond as a quantum sensor. The NV is positioned more than 20 nm below the diamond surface. The diamond has hemispherical shape and is produced by chemical vapor deposition as a solid immersion lens [28], which enhances the excitation and detection efficiency [43,44]. Specifically, we achieve a photon count of up to 1300 kcounts/s from this single NV center. We use two independent radio frequency (RF) generators to generate two time-oscillating signals, which are sent to the diamond and interacts with the NV electron spin. Its spin sublevels $m_s = -1$ and $m_s = 0$ shown in Fig. 2(b) are selected to form an effective qubit sensor.

After the interaction with the signal, we measure the NV sensor spin to extract the transition probability in Eq. (2) and estimate the signal frequencies. Conventional optical readout is performed by detecting its electron spin-dependent fluorescence, but it is affected by photon shot noise. To

overcome this limit, we read out the final state of the NV sensor by employing single shot readout (SSR) [38,45], as illustrated in Fig. 2(c). We use the intrinsic ^{15}N nuclear spin as a memory qubit. In each measurement, the information about the electron spin state is first transferred onto the ^{15}N nuclear spin via an effective controlled-NOT ($C_e\text{NOT}_n$) gate with an electron spin selective π_{RF} pulse on the nuclear spin. Then, the nuclear spin state is detected via SSR with a repetitive readout R times.

Experimentally, we apply a strong magnetic bias field of 598 mT generated by the superconducting magnet, and the ^{15}N nuclear spin average lifetime is extended to approximately 60 ms during single-shot readout, which includes laser illumination [28]. Such a long lifetime allows us to achieve a large number of repetitive readouts of the nuclear spin state with a quantum nondemolition measurement. In our experiments, the nuclear spin readout to detect a given state in a single shot reaches a high fidelity of $\mathcal{F} = 99.69\%$, as shown in Fig. 2(d). We repeat the single measurement $M \approx 4400$ times with a total measurement time of 20 s and extract the averaged transition probability of the NV sensor in Eq. (2) by analyzing the information on the flip rate of the nuclear spin. Our SSR-assisted method yields a nearly twofold enhancement in signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) compared to traditional photoluminescence readout [28], significantly suppressing classical readout noise [see Eq. (3)].

FIG. 3. Demonstration of superresolution condition. (a) The histograms of experimentally measured P_t for frequency separation: $\delta_r/2\pi = [0, 0.5, 1, 2.5, 5]$ kHz. They show apparent (negligible) distinguishability when the superresolution condition is (not) satisfied. (b) Simulated Fisher information, which determines the estimation uncertainty of δ_r , shows gradually increased peaks when the interrogation time t approaches $2n\pi/\delta_s$. Here we set $\delta_s = (2\pi)50$ kHz, $\tilde{\Omega} \approx (2\pi)16.85$ kHz.

Demonstration of superresolution protocol—In a first experiment to demonstrate the superresolution protocol, we generate two independent oscillating signals centered at $\omega_s = (2\pi)5.05$ MHz from the two RF generators with their amplitudes calibrated to be practically identical. The difference between their angular frequencies δ_r varies from $(2\pi)0$ to $(2\pi)5$ kHz. An XY8- N pulse sequence, i.e., XY8, repeated N times with a total of $8N\pi$ pulses, is employed. The spacing of $\tau = 100$ ns between the centers of the π pulses results in a spectral filter centered at $\omega_{\text{DD}} = (2\pi)5$ MHz and subsequently an effective central frequency at $|\delta_s| = \omega_s - \omega_{\text{DD}} = (2\pi)50$ kHz. Thus, the superresolution condition can be fulfilled with an interrogation time of $t = 2n\pi/\delta_s = 20n$ μs , corresponding to $N = 25n$ repetitions of XY8.

We compare the measurement of frequency separation at two different times of P_t , i.e. $t = 2\pi/\delta_s = 20$ μs and $t = 2.56\pi/\delta_s = 25.6$ μs . The estimates of P_t are given by the histograms in Fig. 3(a). When the measurement satisfies the superresolution condition $\delta_s t = 2\pi$, it yields a significantly enhanced response to the frequency separation, allowing for distinguishability of the two frequencies. This is confirmed by the dynamics of Fisher information under the assumption of no classical measurement noise, namely $\mathcal{I}(\delta_r) = (\partial_{\delta_r} P_t)^2 / \sigma_{\text{QPN}}^2$, displaying prominent peaks at these positions, as shown in Fig. 3(b).

Resolution of nearly identical frequencies—In a second experiment, we estimate the sub-kHz frequency difference between two nearly identical incoherent

signals. The center frequency of the two signals is now $\omega_s = (2\pi)2.5125$ MHz and the amplitude is estimated $\tilde{\Omega} \approx (2\pi)16.85$ kHz [28]. The frequency separation takes the values $\delta_r = (2\pi)[0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.5]$ kHz. Similarly, we apply the XY8- N sequence with π pulse spacing of $\tau = 200$ ns ($\omega_{\text{DD}} = (2\pi)2.5$ MHz), shifting the central frequency to $\delta_s = (2\pi)12.5$ kHz. We note that the minimum angular frequency detuning $\delta_s > \delta_{s,\text{min}} \sim (2\pi)/T_2$ is fundamentally constrained by the coherence time of the quantum sensor, where $T_2 \approx 1.3$ ms for the particular XY8 dynamical decoupling sequence we use. In order to reduce errors due to charge-state and count-rate fluctuations, we alternate the phase of the final $\pi/2$ pulse to be 0° or 180° to obtain $1 - P_t$ and P_t , respectively, and subtract them to obtain the signal contrast $C_t = (1 - P_t) - P_t = \prod_{i=1}^2 J_0 \left[(4\tilde{\Omega}/\delta_i) \sin(\delta_i t/2) \right]$, where $\delta_i = \omega_{\text{DD}} - \omega_i$. In Fig. 4(a), we show the evolution of C_t vs total interaction time. The contrast shows a maximal response to the frequency separation at $t = 80$ μs , which satisfies the superresolution condition $t = 2\pi/\delta_s$.

Next, we fix the evolution time at $t = 80$ μs and perform 30 measurements of C_t for every δ_r to obtain an average, reducing the statistical uncertainty, as shown in Fig. 4(b). The contrast is normalized to the case without a signal. The experimentally measured contrast C_t fits excellently the theoretical values. Next, we estimate the frequency separation from these measured C_t , resulting in $\delta_r \approx \delta_s \sqrt{1 - C_t} / (\sqrt{2}\tilde{\Omega}t)$. Figure 4(c) demonstrates that the estimated frequency differences match excellently with their actual values. We note that we estimate the frequency separation using Eq. (2) for large values of δ_r , where the contrast is lower than 0.5 [28]. The uncertainty of the estimated frequency difference is

$$\Delta\delta_r \approx \frac{\delta_s}{2\sqrt{2}\tilde{\Omega}t} \frac{\Delta C_t}{\sqrt{1 - C_t}} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}\tilde{\Omega}t^2} \frac{\Delta C_t}{\sqrt{1 - C_t}}, \quad (6)$$

where we neglect the uncertainties in δ_s and $\tilde{\Omega}$, which is feasible for small δ_r [28]. We depict the estimation uncertainty (simulated $\Delta\delta_r$ bounded by the FI) in Fig. 4(d). The experimental data exhibit excellent agreement with the simulation. We note that FI does not remain constant for very small values of δ_r due to other noise sources apart from QPN, e.g., decoherence and residual classical readout noise, leading to an increase in the experimental estimation error. As shown in Fig. 4(d), a simulation accounting for decoherence fits excellently the experimental values in this regime [28]. Based on the latter simulation and the resolution criterion $\Delta\delta_r \leq |\delta_r|$, we estimate the best achievable frequency resolution of $(2\pi)23.3$ Hz. The experimental data and simulations at $t = 2.56\pi/\delta_s$ when the superresolution condition is not satisfied demonstrate a much higher estimation uncertainty, as expected from theory. The experiments clearly

FIG. 4. (a) Signal contrast vs total measurement time t with dynamical decoupling with pulse separation $\tau = \pi/\omega_{\text{DD}} = 200$ ns for different δ_r . The maximum difference is at the superresolution time of $t = 2\pi/\delta_s = 80 \mu\text{s}$. (b) Experimental (red dots) and simulated (green line) signal contrast at $t = 80 \mu\text{s}$ vs angular frequency difference δ_r . (c) Estimated vs actual frequency separation δ_r . We note that the approximation $\delta_r \ll \delta_s$ is not valid for $\delta_r = (2\pi)2.5$ kHz. (d) Estimation uncertainty $\Delta\delta_r$ vs δ_r , which is consistent with Eq. (3). The green squares and line represent the measured and simulated $\Delta\delta_r$ at $t = 2.56\pi/\delta_s$ under the assumption of perfect measurements, corresponding to the data in Fig. 3(a). The thin gray line shows simulations for an increased interaction time $t = 2.56\pi/\delta_s = 102.4 \mu\text{s}$. The red dots represent the experimental data at the superresolution condition. The red solid line shows the simulated $\Delta\delta_r$ derived from the theoretical Fisher information under the assumption of perfect measurements with the same experimental parameters. The red dashed line represents the simulated $\Delta\delta_r$ obtained by incorporating the decoherence of the quantum sensor [28], showing excellent agreement with the experimental results.

demonstrate the advantage of our protocol, allowing for significantly improved resolution, e.g., in nanoscale NMR.

Conclusion—We demonstrate the principles of superresolution quantum sensing with a solid-state single spin quantum sensor by experimentally resolving two incoherent signals with nearly identical frequencies. We use single-shot readout, assisted by the intrinsic ^{15}N nuclear spin as memory to limit classical readout noise. The protocol nearly eliminates quantum projection noise by quantum control, leading to a finite Fisher information even when the frequencies are arbitrarily close. These findings establish a practical framework for high-resolution nano-NMR, advancing the capabilities of quantum spectroscopy in detecting closely spaced spectral features, which can be related to J coupling or chemical shift. The uncertainty of the frequency separation improves as $\Delta\delta_r \sim t^{-2}$ with the superresolution method in comparison to t^{-1} with standard approaches. Resolution can be improved even further with a prolonged interrogation time, which can reach more than a millisecond for electronic spin sensors [46–48]. We note that spin-squeezed or entangled states with ensembles of NV centers as quantum probes have already been demonstrated [49–51] and could in principle be combined with

our superresolution protocol for further improvement of sensitivity. Employing squeezed states of light has also allowed to surpass the standard quantum limit in other systems [52–54], but these methods go beyond the scope of our Letter. We implement the method in the context of pulsed dynamical decoupling and Ramsey sequences, enabling detection frequencies from dc to several tens of MHz [1]. Extending these techniques to higher-frequency domains in the GHz range might also be possible by using appropriate sequences [48,55], highlighting the broad applications of the method.

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Data availability—The data that support the findings of this article are not publicly available. The data are available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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